

**TECHNOLOGIES FOR IMPROVING THE TEACHING OF THE
SCIENTIFIC AND PEDAGOGICAL CREATIVITY OF EASTERN
THINKERS**

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the technologies for improving the teaching of the scientific and pedagogical creativity of Eastern thinkers and their use in the educational system of Uzbekistan. The article considers new methods of studying the works of thinkers based on modern educational methods, innovative technologies and international experiences.

Key words: innovative approaches, Eastern thinkers, scientific-pedagogical creativity, teaching, textbooks and training manuals.

Introduction

In the works of Eastern thinkers, methods such as conversations, lectures, explanations, and advice were often used to shape individual consciousness. These methods are relevant in the educational process to develop students' knowledge, skills, and competencies. The main goal is to cultivate moral, ethical, social-economic, physical, and aesthetic aspects in individuals and to develop the ability to evaluate events and behaviors correctly.

Modern Educational Technologies

Special Educational Programs: Special educational programs are developed to deeply study the works of thinkers, incorporating interactive methods, video

lessons, and illustrations. For example, using visual materials to teach Avicenna's contributions to medicine and philosophy enhances student engagement.

Online Platforms and Digital Resources: The works of Eastern thinkers are being digitized and made widely available through online platforms. These platforms feature interactive lessons, videos, and e-books. Virtual reality (VR) and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies further enhance the learning process. For instance, VR can bring to life Avicenna's medical discoveries or Ulugh Beg's astronomical research.

Interactive Educational Technologies: Interactive lessons, virtual labs, and simulations help apply the works of thinkers in practice. For example, using virtual astronomy lessons based on Ulugh Beg's "Zij-i-Sultani" helps students better understand astronomical calculations.

Integrated Approaches in Education

The works of Eastern thinkers are taught in integration with various subjects. For instance, Al-Khwarizmi's algebra in mathematics classes or Al-Biruni's geographical research in history classes.

Problem-Based Learning (PBL): This methodology encourages students to solve problems independently and develop critical thinking. For example, studying Avicenna's approach to medical problems can inspire students to find new solutions.

Educational Resources and Manuals

Special Textbooks and Manuals: Special textbooks and manuals are being prepared based on the works of Eastern thinkers. These resources are designed according to modern teaching methodologies, aimed at deeply studying the scientific works of the thinkers.

Interactive Educational Materials: Interactive lessons and activities help students better assimilate the material. For instance, studying Ulugh Beg's

astronomical calculations interactively helps students understand their essence better.

International Cooperation and Experience Exchange

International conferences and seminars are helping to study and popularize the scientific heritage of Eastern thinkers. Through these events, scholars and researchers from various countries exchange experiences. Universities and research centers in Uzbekistan are organizing internships for students and teachers in collaboration with foreign higher education institutions. These internships provide opportunities to study the scientific heritage of Eastern thinkers more deeply.

Conclusion

Efforts to improve the teaching of the scientific and pedagogical creativity of Eastern thinkers in Uzbekistan are based on modern technologies and innovative approaches. These efforts will help future generations assimilate the rich scientific heritage of the thinkers.

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